

**PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION
IN PRIMARY CLASSES AND ITS MANAGEMENT**

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Abstract. The article examines the importance of improving the methodical training and professional development of primary school teachers as a scientific-pedagogical problem and pedagogical foundations. It summarizes the opinions of foreign and local researchers. Based on the principles of professional development of primary school teachers, the quality of education in primary schools and the theoretical and pedagogical aspects of its management are scientifically based.

Key words: quality of education, pedagogical skills, lesson efficiency, methodical training.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted, "In developed countries, great attention is paid to investing in the full cycle of education, i.e. investing in the education of a child from 3 to 22 years old. 17 times more profitable. In our case, this indicator is only 4 times. The quality of education is a comprehensive socio-pedagogical process that determines the state and results of education. The quality of education is a set of characteristics that satisfy the human need and the interests of society and the state. If we touch upon the concept of educational efficiency along with the quality of education, these concepts differ from each other and are determined by the ratio of the quality

result to the goal, while efficiency is determined by the ratio of the result to the costs and resources spent. At this point, it is appropriate to mention the plan of effective management actions of the teacher during the educational process: goal setting - determination of didactic tasks, formation of educational results. This is the main factor of pedagogical activity and directs the joint activity of the teacher and the learner to a common result; - diagnosis - studying the characteristics of learners and available material and technical possibilities. This allows you to choose the necessary goal adjustments and the means to achieve them

- forecasting - predicting the results of pedagogical and educational activities in the existing conditions within the set time

- planning - creating a future activity model, choosing ways and means within the time set in existing conditions, dividing the stages of achieving the goal, forming separate tasks for them, determining the means and ways of delivering educational information and feedback - planning

- will consist of developing a plan for future interrelated pedagogical and educational activities. It is formalized in the form of a technological map; Organization is the involvement of students in the specified work by the teacher, cooperation with them in achieving the specified goal. Informational provision

- implementation of ways and means of delivery of educational information and feedback.

It allows to quickly change the course of the collected information process, to introduce influencing factors and effective tools;

- control, evaluation and change

- creation of motivating factors affecting the development process, coordinating the change of the object of pedagogical influence;

- analysis of the completed process

- it is appropriate to mention inefficiencies, the reasons for their occurrence, and measures to prevent them in the next iteration.

The quality of education is a complex process consisting of the integrity of its characteristics, the combination of the most convenient methods that serve the student's learning and personal development. The quality of education and its management is an important condition for the development of society and determines its intellectual, spiritual and cultural level. Intellectual of the state taking into account that the quality of education ensures its potential, continuously improving the effectiveness of education, making changes in accordance with international standards, implementing innovative approaches will significantly increase the dynamics of its development. The more attention is paid to the quality of education at the level of the state, region, and institution, the more effective the expenses spent on its improvement will be, and the result will be in line with international standards. One of the effective ways to improve the quality of education is to create conditions for students to conduct independent creative activities in the course of lessons under the guidance of educators. In order to achieve this goal, the first task is to create an environment that will increase the educational activity of students and develop the quality of education. Among them, we need to improve the skills of both the textbook and the pedagogue in order for primary education students to receive quality education. Every education, that is, knowledge given in primary classes, is either a punishment or a great achievement for us in the future. Pedagogical activity of the educator is adapted to the activity of the learners. Words of I. A. Karimov: Education and training are like a bird. One wing of a bird is education, one wing is education. If one wing falls, the bird dies. should go Where there is education, there is definitely education. If he improves his pedagogic skills to elementary school students, uses various methods in the educational process, and teaches interesting and more difficult subjects in easy ways, the pedagogue will definitely help each student to master the subject well. Conclusion: today's educational textbooks for elementary grades, i.e. newly developed books, are very colorful, interesting, rich

in information and attract students with their new methods and allow them to get quality education. As one of the most important conditions for increasing the effectiveness of education in general education institutions, it is necessary to pay attention to the establishment of an effective cooperation mechanism to unite the participants of the educational process with each other. Today, primary school teachers expect clearly evidenced, science-based instruction from the methodology. The methodology allows the future elementary school teacher to be able to independently consciously approach the content of literary education and its teaching, not only to study the experience of others, but also to consciously analyze the results of their activities and make the right conclusion. ensures that they are able to produce. Each pedagogue has his own methods and manuals, and if he can attract the student in different situations, he will definitely get the expected result from the lesson.

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